

Negative Kinetic Energy and Bound Quantum States

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For the case of a harmonic oscillator and also for tunneling from a square well potential, one notices a negative kinetic energy beyond the classical turning point. In previous notes, we argued one may write the Schrodinger equation as:

$-p^2 \psi + \sum_{j+k=p} V_k f_j = E \psi$ ((1)) where V_k is the k th Fourier transform of the potential and

$W(x)=\text{wavefunction} = \sum_j f_k \exp(i k x)$ in one dimension.

In this note, we examine ((1)) which shows the “granularity” of the interactions with the averaged $V(x)$ and try to determine why a quantum particle should penetrate beyond a classical turning point.

Conditional Probabilities

In previous notes, we argued that quantum mechanics is associated with two channel periodic behaviour i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. This leads to a complex conditional probability:

$$\langle pp \rangle = [\sum_{p'} p'^2 \psi_{p'} \exp(ipx)] / [\sum_{p'} \psi_{p'} \exp(ipx)] \quad ((2))$$

$\langle pp \rangle / 2m$ is the average kinetic energy which satisfies a conservation of energy equation (for average quantities) for a bound state situation, namely:

$$\langle pp \rangle / 2m + V(x) = E_n \quad ((3))$$

((3)) is identical to the bound state Schrodinger equation and uses only average quantities such as E , $V(x)$ and $\langle pp \rangle / 2m$. It seems, however, that quantum mechanics may be based on “fluctuations” and that considering only the average situation, although it leads to a solvable equation, perhaps obscures some of the physics. For example, one may argue a particle placed in a box with infinite potential walls interacts with the wall in such a way that many different $\exp(ipx)$ states are created. This has been argued in the literature. Thus, if one takes this granularity seriously, one may consider the conditional probability: $P(p/x)$. Let us first assume that $P(p/x)$ is a positive real number and that $\sum_p P(p/x) = 1$.

It is also known experimentally, that the density profile for such a particle in a box with infinite potential at the walls is proportional to $\sin(k_{ave} x) \sin(k_{ave} x)$. Thus, $P(p/x) = 0$ for all p at zeros of $\sin(k_{ave} x)$. Furthermore, $\langle pp \rangle = 0$ at these zeros.

Now: $\langle p^2 \rangle = [\text{Sum over } p \quad p^* p P(p/x)] / W(x)$ ((4)), but $p^* p > 0$ always so $P(p/x)$ must take on positive and negative values. This immediately contradicts the assumption that $P(p/x) > 0$. Thus, in quantum mechanics, unusual things seem to be occurring with conditional probabilities. There seems to be positive and negative probability values as well as periodicity.

Bound State in a Square Well Potential

The bound particle in a square well potential problem is well known. The potential is $-V_0$ from $x=0$ to $x=a$ and 0 outside. Thus, $d/dx V(x) = 0$ for $x > a$. Nevertheless, the wavefunction exists for $x > a$, although it is exponentially damped. In other words, a particle may exist outside of the well, but it is apparently not free. This leads to interpretation problems, even though one may solve the Schrodinger equation $(-1/2m) d/dx d/dx W(x) + V(x) W(x) = E W(x)$ ((4)) in both regions. For instance:

$$W(x) = A \sin(k_1 x + b) \text{ for } 0 \leq x \leq a \quad \text{and} \quad W(x) = B \exp(-k_2 x) \text{ for } x > a$$

One matches $W(x)$ and $d/dx W(x)$ at the boundary. The energy is negative and the same in both regions.

(Alternatively, one may consider a problem for which the potential $V=0$ for $0 \leq x \leq a$ and $V=\text{constant}$ $x > a$. This is usually the tunneling scenario)

This leads to interpretation issues. Negative energy is called binding energy and is clear in the region $0 \leq x \leq a$, but what does it mean to have negative energy for $x > a$? According to ((4)), the particle in $x > a$ experiences no potential and hence no force in this region. How is it still bound, only through the negative energy which implies negative kinetic energy? What does negative kinetic energy mean?

We suggest some of these questions arise because the Schrodinger equation ((4)) is in a form showing averages. The presence of $(-1/2m) d/dx d/dx W(x)$ as average kinetic energy seems to imply, however, that something else is occurring. In particular, if one writes $W(x)$ as a Fourier series:

$$\text{KE average} = (1/2m) \text{Sum over } p \quad p^* p f_p \exp(ipx) \quad ((4a))$$

If one takes ((4a)) as representing a physical situation, it seems to suggest the particle is knocked from one p plane wave state into another. (One does not have to think of $\exp(ipx)$ as a plane wave, but could consider it to represent an object with two independent channels linked with each other in a periodic manner.)

In other words $V(x)$ is the average potential, but we argue that if one writes $V(x)$ and $W(x)$ as Fourier series, one has from the Schrodinger equation:

$$p^* p / 2m f_p + \text{Sum } j+k V_k f_j = E f_p \quad ((5))$$

This appears to be a microscopic equation with only one average quantity, E . This average E thus seems to play an important role in microscopic picture as well as in the factor $\exp(i E t)$. In ((5)), the average potential no longer appears, but rather V_k , the k th Fourier transform associated with the wavelength $k=6.28/L$. Thus, there are lengths associated with each Fourier transform, even though one may get a sharp edge for $V(x)$ at $x=a$ when one takes an overall average. This may help to explain why a particle may penetrate the barrier. A particle moves from one p state to another ($\exp(ipx)$) according to ((5)) and so is not blocked from moving past $x=a$. ((5)), however, governs the probability which dies down exponentially in the region $x>a$. Even in this region, the particle is entwined in a resonance with the potential governed by the average energy E . Though the average kinetic energy is negative in this region, the particle is knocked from one $\exp(ipx)$ state to another by the potential and each of these states has a kinetic energy of $p^2/2m$. The probability $P(p/x) = \int \exp(ipx) W(x)$ must then be responsible for the overall average negative kinetic energy.

Negative Kinetic Energy for the Oscillator

The presence of an average negative kinetic energy does not only occur for tunnelling type of situations. The harmonic oscillator also has an average negative kinetic energy when the quantum particle passes the classical turning point. Consider the ground state wavefunction $W(x)$ proportional to $\exp(-.5\sqrt{km}xx)$. Then:

$$\text{Average KE} = -1/2m [-\sqrt{km} + (km)xx] \quad ((6))$$

The average KE is zero when $x= 1/\sqrt{km}$ and become negative after that point for increasing x . In a classical system, once the kinetic energy is 0, the particle changes direction. It should be pointed out that the wavefunction is highly damped $\exp(-axx)$ as x increases. If one considers ((5)), then the particle may interact with the potential past the point of KE average=0.

It should also be pointed out that $\exp(-.5\sqrt{km}xx)$ squared is of the form of the Boltzmann factor $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ for an oscillator. In the temperature case, there is kinetic energy which can shift any particular gas particle from one momentum state to another, thus one does not have classical turning points from the oscillator for the gas particles. It seems the "temperature" in statistical mechanics plays a similar role to the potential $V(x)$ in the quantum case in providing stochastic momentum transfers to a particle. Thus, the two models (statistical mechanics and quantum mechanics) seem similar for the ground state oscillator.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have tried to picture the Schrodinger equation in terms of a quantum particle undergoing stochastic "hits" from a potential governed by ((4)). This is different from considering the idea of an average potential and may help to explain why a quantum particle may move past

a point at which its average kinetic energy is zero (e.g. tunneling and the oscillator) unlike the classical case.